

Insights into oxidative protein modifications in shellfish allergens: Impact of GI digestion following thermal treatment

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Protein modifications (PMs) are covalent changes occurring on amino acid (AA) side chains of proteins via enzymatic action or spontaneously. They increase the protein structure complexity from the level of the genome to the proteome, and can determine their activity and, interactions¹. It has been shown, on myofibrillar fish proteins that oxidative modifications depending on their saturation can decrease or enhance protein digestibility². Thus in this study shellfish meat samples were subjected to cooking followed by simulated INFOGEST *in vitro* gastrointestinal digestion protocol. Mass Spectrometry and in gel based proteomics, were used to detect PMs and digestion resistant peptides of raw and cooked shellfish meat samples with a focus on major shellfish allergens: sarcoplasmic calcium-binding protein (SBP) and tropomyosin (TPM). Lastly, identified PMs were marked on TPM alignment from shrimp, oyster and abalone species, to gain insight into their pattern on the known IgE binding epitopes. Focusing on oxidative PMs, mostly on oxidation of Met, it was confirmed that, in all shellfish samples, PMs on TPM and SBP were more predominant after cooking. For instance in abalone, double oxidation of Met was only detected in cooked samples (sulfone M68 and M81). Another indicator of oxidative stress, 4-hydroxynonenal (HNE), was identified on shrimp TPM and, notably HNE was 21 times more abundant in the cooked sample. Study highlights the susceptibility of immunodominant epitopes in major shellfish allergens to oxidative PMs, which could impact interactions with the immune system in sensitive individuals. Significant resistance to digestion was demonstrated by paramyosin fragments in abalone and oyster suggesting the need for further analysis of their allergenicity. SBP of raw shrimp was strikingly resistant to both gastric and intestinal digestion. Moreover, our results indicate that oxidative modifications may decrease the stability of proteins like shrimp TPM, making them more digestible in thermally treated samples, highlighting a potential strategy for reducing allergenicity.

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